

ASEAN-China Relations in the Post-Cold War Era: From Suspicion to an Asymmetric Cooperation Model

Vuong Quoc Khanh ✉
Law and Management School, Thu Dau Mot University, Vietnam

Abstract

This article analyzes the evolution of ASEAN–China relations in the post–Cold War period, emphasizing the transition from mutual suspicion to the emergence of an asymmetric cooperation model. Drawing on a synthesis and analysis of political, economic, and security developments in the region, the study shows that the relationship has progressed through stages of normalization, expanded cooperation, and the establishment of a strategic partnership. In this process, economic cooperation—particularly through the ASEAN–China Free Trade Area (ACFTA) and ASEAN+3 mechanisms—has played a central role in promoting regional integration and providing a foundation for stability. However, security issues, especially disputes in the South China Sea, remain a persistent source of strategic mistrust between the two sides. The article argues that contemporary ASEAN–China relations reflect a model of asymmetric cooperation, in which disparities in power are managed through regional institutional arrangements and cooperative frameworks. While this model contributes to maintaining relative stability, it also contains inherent limitations arising from divergent interests and the broader dynamics of great power competition.

Keywords: *ASEAN–China relations, Asymmetric cooperation, Post–Cold War Southeast Asia, Regional order.*

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Introduction

In the aftermath of the Cold War, Southeast Asia has undergone profound transformations in its regional order and power structure, with ASEAN–China relations emerging as one of the most consequential axes of interaction. From a state of suspicion and confrontation in earlier periods, the two sides have gradually established dialogue, expanded cooperation, and moved toward a strategic partnership. However, this trajectory has not been linear; rather, it reflects a complex interplay of cooperation and competition within an increasingly asymmetrical power context (Tru, 2009; Sutter, 2005).

Scholarship on Southeast Asian regional order emphasizes ASEAN’s role as a central coordinating actor, grounded in the norms of the “ASEAN Way,” including consensus, non-interference, and preventive diplomacy (Acharya, 2001; Caballero-Anthony, 2022). At the same time, China’s rise has significantly reshaped the regional strategic environment, posing challenges to ASEAN centrality and prompting Southeast Asian states to recalibrate their strategic responses (Goldstein, 2005; Zha, 2023). Within this context, analytical frameworks such as balancing, bandwagoning, and hedging have been widely employed to explain the behavior of regional actors (Goh, 2016; Kuik, 2021).

At the empirical level, ASEAN–China relations are simultaneously driven by deepening economic cooperation and constrained by persistent security concerns, particularly disputes in the South China Sea. Institutional mechanisms such as the Declaration on the Conduct of Parties in the South China Sea (DOC) are widely regarded as efforts to manage conflict and maintain regional stability, even though they do not resolve underlying sovereignty disputes (ASEAN, 2002; Buszynski, 2003; Fravel, 2011). This

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dynamic reveals a distinctive relational pattern in which cooperation coexists with enduring strategic distrust (Hayton, 2014; Nam, 2011).

Against this backdrop, this article addresses the following questions: how have ASEAN–China relations evolved in the post–Cold War period, and what characterizes the current model of interaction? The article argues that these relations have transitioned from mutual suspicion toward a form of asymmetric cooperation, in which power disparities are mediated through institutional mechanisms and regional cooperation frameworks. In doing so, the study contributes to a more nuanced understanding of Southeast Asia’s regional order amid intensifying great power competition.

Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative approach to examine the evolution of ASEAN–China relations in the post–Cold War context. A qualitative methodology is particularly appropriate as it enables a nuanced analysis of structural, institutional, and strategic behavioral factors—dimensions that are difficult to quantify but are crucial to understanding the formation and functioning of regional order (Acharya, 2001; Caballero-Anthony, 2022). Accordingly, the study focuses on explaining patterns of interaction among regional actors under conditions of power asymmetry, rather than measuring quantitative variables.

The empirical basis of the study primarily consists of secondary sources selected according to their relevance to the research topic. Specifically, the analysis draws on (i) international scholarly works on regional order, China’s strategic behavior, and ASEAN’s role (Goh, 2007; Johnston, 2003; Goldstein, 2005; Kuik, 2021); (ii) specialized studies on the South China Sea and conflict management (Buszynski, 2003; Emmers, 2007; Fravel, 2011; Hayton, 2014); and (iii) Vietnamese academic and policy-oriented literature to provide a regional perspective (Tru, 2009; Hai, 2009; Nam, 2011; Binh, 2008). In addition, official documents—most notably the Declaration on the Conduct of Parties in the South China Sea (DOC)—are utilized to identify shared norms of behavior and institutional frameworks endorsed by the parties involved (ASEAN, 2002).

Data collection follows a purposive sampling strategy, prioritizing sources with high scholarly credibility and direct relevance to the research questions. The materials are categorized into three main groups: (i) theoretical works on regional order and power asymmetry; (ii) analyses of China’s strategy and behavior; and (iii) studies on cooperation and conflict in ASEAN–China relations. This classification ensures both systematic organization and analytical consistency.

In terms of analytical methods, the study employs content analysis and historical-comparative analysis to identify patterns of interaction and transformation over time. Content analysis is used to clarify key concepts such as cooperation, suspicion, and asymmetry as reflected in academic literature and official documents, while the historical approach situates these dynamics within the broader trajectory of regional development (Curley & Thomas, 2007; Jones & Smith, 2006). In addition, a case study approach is applied through the examination of the Mischief Reef dispute, which serves as an empirical illustration of the shift from confrontation to institutionalized conflict management at the regional level (Hai, 2009).

While the qualitative approach enables an in-depth exploration of underlying mechanisms and interaction patterns, it also entails certain limitations, particularly the reliance on secondary data and the difficulty of assessing the relative impact of individual factors. Nevertheless, by combining diverse data sources with complementary analytical techniques, the study ensures both analytical robustness and explanatory relevance in addressing the research questions.

Findings

From Suspicion to Normalization (pre-1991 – early 2000s)

Prior to the end of the Cold War, ASEAN–China relations were largely characterized by suspicion and ideological confrontation. During this period, China was often perceived as a destabilizing force in

Southeast Asia, particularly due to its support for communist movements in the region. As a result, ASEAN member states maintained strategic distance and prioritized alignment with external powers to ensure their security (Tru, 2009; Binh, 2008). Within this context, the regional structure was highly polarized and dominated by major powers, limiting the prospects for an autonomous regional cooperation framework (Jones & Smith, 2006).

The end of the Cold War marked a critical turning point, creating opportunities to restructure relations between ASEAN and China. China's adjustment of its foreign policy toward a "peaceful rise" and its emphasis on stabilizing its surrounding environment contributed to reducing tensions and facilitating dialogue (Sutter, 2005). At the same time, ASEAN gradually shifted from a confrontational posture to a more inclusive approach, recognizing China as a necessary partner in an emerging regional order (Curley & Thomas, 2007).

The normalization process became evident through the establishment of formal dialogue mechanisms in the early 1990s. China became a dialogue partner of ASEAN in 1991, signaling a transition from confrontation to institutionalized cooperation. This development was not only symbolic but also reflected a broader shift in strategic perceptions on both sides: ASEAN sought a stable environment conducive to development, while China aimed to build trust and avoid triggering balancing responses from regional actors (Johnston, 2003; Sutter, 2005).

Nevertheless, this process was not entirely smooth and remained shaped by persistent elements of mutual suspicion. Existing studies indicate that during this period, China simultaneously pursued regional integration and safeguarded its core security interests, particularly concerning sovereignty and strategic influence (Johnston, 2003). This duality produced a pattern of "cooperation with caution," laying the foundation for the distinctive nature of ASEAN–China relations in subsequent periods.

From a structural perspective, this phase also reflected a transition from a polarized order toward a more flexible regional configuration, in which regional institutions began to play an increasingly significant role in regulating interactions among actors (Curley & Thomas, 2007). ASEAN, as an evolving regional organization, gradually asserted its centrality by creating platforms for dialogue and promoting multilateral cooperation. This contributed to reducing direct confrontation and expanding the space for more constructive engagement between ASEAN and China.

Overall, the period from before 1991 to the early 2000s marked a shift from suspicion to normalization in ASEAN–China relations. Although comprehensive cooperation mechanisms had not yet fully developed, the changes in perceptions and behavior during this phase laid a crucial foundation for subsequent institutionalization and deeper engagement. This transformation was not merely a product of changes in the international environment but also reflected strategic adjustments by both ASEAN and China within an evolving regional order.

Institutionalizing ASEAN–China Cooperation

Following the normalization of relations, ASEAN and China entered a new phase characterized by the rapid expansion of cooperative mechanisms and the institutionalization of both bilateral and multilateral engagement. This transition reflects not only the need to build mutual trust but also ASEAN's efforts to maintain its central role within an evolving regional order (Acharya, 2001; Caballero-Anthony, 2022).

One of the most significant developments in this process has been the establishment and expansion of ASEAN–China dialogue frameworks. Mechanisms such as ASEAN+1 and ASEAN+3 have provided regular platforms for exchanges on political, economic, and security issues. These frameworks have not only facilitated substantive cooperation but have also contributed to shaping norms of interaction grounded in consensus and preventive diplomacy—core features of the "ASEAN Way" (Acharya, 2001; Natalegawa, 2018). Through these mechanisms, ASEAN has gradually constructed an institutional space in which major powers, including China, are engaged on the basis of shared rules, albeit with limited binding force.

In the security domain, the signing of the Declaration on the Conduct of Parties in the South China Sea (DOC) in 2002 represents a critical milestone in the institutionalization of conflict management between ASEAN and China. Although the DOC lacks strong legal enforceability, it establishes fundamental principles such as restraint, peaceful dispute settlement, and the promotion of confidence-building measures (ASEAN, 2002). A substantial body of scholarship suggests that the core value of the DOC lies more in its normative function than in its legal effect, as it creates a shared behavioral framework in a context where sovereignty disputes remain unresolved (Buszynski, 2003; Emmers, 2007).

This process of institutionalization also reflects ASEAN's adaptive response to a changing security environment. Recent studies indicate that the "ASEAN Way" is not a static model but has evolved to accommodate new pressures, including China's rise and intensifying great power competition (Caballero-Anthony, 2022). In this context, the promotion of flexible and non-binding institutional arrangements enables ASEAN to preserve internal consensus while simultaneously engaging China within an inclusive cooperative framework.

However, China's participation in ASEAN-led mechanisms remains selective and strategic. Beijing engages in these institutional frameworks to avoid diplomatic isolation and maintain a stable regional environment, while carefully avoiding commitments that might constrain its strategic autonomy (Natalegawa, 2018). This dynamic produces a defining feature of ASEAN–China relations: institutional mechanisms exist and function, but their effectiveness depends largely on the voluntary compliance of participating actors.

Moreover, institutionalization has transformed the way conflicts are managed in the region. Rather than addressing disputes solely at the bilateral level, ASEAN has promoted the multilateralization and institutionalization of security issues, thereby creating a broader space for dialogue. This approach reduces the likelihood of escalation while reinforcing ASEAN's role as a regional "convener" and coordinator (Acharya, 2001; Emmers, 2007).

Overall, the institutionalization phase of ASEAN–China cooperation marks a significant shift from ad hoc interactions toward more structured frameworks of engagement. Although these mechanisms remain limited in terms of legal bindingness, they play an essential role in building trust, managing conflict, and maintaining relative stability in ASEAN–China relations. In this sense, institutionalization serves not only as a tool of cooperation but also as a foundational element in the emergence of an asymmetric model of relations in subsequent periods.

Economic Cooperation and Growing Interdependence

Alongside the institutionalization of relations, economic cooperation between ASEAN and China has expanded rapidly and has become one of the most significant pillars of their bilateral engagement. The sharp increase in trade, investment, and economic linkages has not only contributed to regional growth but has also generated an increasingly dense pattern of interdependence between the two sides. As China has risen as a major economic power, ASEAN has both benefited from expanded market opportunities and been compelled to adjust its strategies in response to shifting power dynamics (Goldstein, 2005; Goh, 2007).

One of the most prominent manifestations of this economic cooperation is the establishment of the ASEAN–China Free Trade Area (ACFTA), which officially came into effect in 2010. ACFTA has significantly boosted trade flows between the two sides, making China one of ASEAN's largest trading partners. This development reflects a broader trend toward deepening regional economic integration while creating a complex web of shared interests between ASEAN economies and China. A growing body of research suggests that such interdependence helps reduce incentives for direct confrontation, thereby contributing to regional stability (Goldstein, 2005; Ha & Hung, 2025).

From a theoretical perspective, the rise of interdependence can be understood as a key component of Southeast Asian states' adaptive strategies in response to China's rise. Rather than adopting confrontational approaches, ASEAN countries tend to combine economic cooperation with strategic caution to maximize benefits and mitigate risks. Studies on "hedging" strategies indicate that small and

medium-sized states often maintain a flexible balance among major powers, with economic engagement serving as an important tool for managing uncertainty (Goh, 2016; Kuik, 2021).

Beyond trade, regional economic initiatives such as ASEAN+3 and subregional cooperation programs—particularly in the Mekong area—have further strengthened economic and infrastructural connectivity between ASEAN and China. These mechanisms not only promote economic development but also reinforce China’s role as an indispensable partner in the regional economic architecture (Goh, 2007). However, China’s expanding role also highlights increasing asymmetries in economic capabilities, as many ASEAN economies become more dependent on Chinese markets and capital.

Recent surveys of regional perceptions indicate that Southeast Asian countries view China simultaneously as a crucial economic partner and a source of strategic risk. The report by Seah et al. (2024) shows that while China is widely recognized for its economic importance, concerns regarding its political and security influence persist across the region. This dual perception reflects a core characteristic of ASEAN–China relations: the coexistence of economic interdependence and strategic distrust.

In the context of intensifying U.S.–China competition, ASEAN continues to adjust its strategies to maintain a balance among major powers. Recent studies suggest that ASEAN does not align exclusively with any single power but instead adopts a flexible approach aimed at preserving its interests and strategic autonomy (Ha & Hung, 2025). Economic cooperation with China, therefore, carries not only developmental significance but also constitutes a broader strategic response to an increasingly competitive geopolitical environment.

Overall, economic cooperation and growing interdependence have played a crucial role in stabilizing ASEAN–China relations. However, this interdependence is inherently asymmetrical, given China’s overwhelming advantages in economic scale and capacity. As a result, while economic ties function as a “binding force” in bilateral relations, they simultaneously generate concerns and strategic recalibrations on the part of ASEAN.

From Cooperation to Asymmetry: Security Tensions and the Emergence of an Asymmetric Relationship Model

Despite the expansion of economic cooperation and institutionalization, security issues—particularly disputes in the South China Sea—continue to shape the fundamentally asymmetric nature of ASEAN–China relations. The South China Sea is not only a site of overlapping sovereignty claims but also a space where power disparities between China and ASEAN states are most visibly manifested, as well as where the limitations of regional governance mechanisms become apparent (Fravel, 2011; Hayton, 2014).

Existing studies indicate that China pursues a strategy that combines institutional engagement with the protection of core security interests. While participating in regional mechanisms such as the DOC, China simultaneously undertakes activities aimed at consolidating its sovereignty claims and strengthening its on-the-ground presence in the South China Sea (Fravel, 2011). This reflects a consistent strategic logic of a rising power: to utilize institutions as tools for stabilizing the external environment, while avoiding commitments that could constrain its freedom of action (Mearsheimer, 2001; Zha, 2023).

Empirical developments in the South China Sea suggest that existing institutional mechanisms are capable of managing conflict only to a limited extent. Although the DOC establishes principles such as restraint and peaceful dispute settlement, its lack of legal bindingness means that its effectiveness depends largely on voluntary compliance by the parties involved (Beckman & Schofield, 2014). Studies on conflict management further highlight that current approaches prioritize “management” rather than “resolution,” reflecting the structural constraints faced by regional institutions under conditions of power asymmetry (Hayton, 2014; Nam, 2011).

The 1995 Mischief Reef incident serves as a representative case illustrating the shift from confrontation to institutionalized conflict management in ASEAN–China relations. The incident not only heightened tensions between China and the Philippines but also prompted ASEAN to move from bilateral handling

toward the multilateralization of regional security issues (Hai, 2009). Through this process, ASEAN gradually assumed the role of a coordinating actor, despite lacking strong enforcement capabilities.

In addition, China's long-term strategic objectives—including the expansion of maritime influence and the pursuit of energy security—have further reinforced asymmetries in the region. Some studies suggest that initiatives such as the “String of Pearls” strategy reflect China's efforts to extend its strategic presence beyond its immediate periphery (Tien, 2012). These developments have heightened concerns among ASEAN states, particularly in the context of intensifying great power competition.

From a structural perspective, asymmetry in ASEAN–China relations stems not only from disparities in material capabilities but also from differences in the ability to shape regional norms and rules. Theories of international relations suggest that in systems characterized by uneven power distribution, major powers possess greater latitude to adjust their behavior in line with their interests (Mearsheimer, 2001). In contrast, smaller states must rely on adaptive strategies and institutional mechanisms to navigate such an environment.

Taken together, ASEAN–China relations have evolved from cooperation toward a clearly asymmetric model. Within this framework, cooperation and competition coexist, with institutional mechanisms playing a regulatory role but unable to eliminate conflict entirely. This reflects a distinctive form of regional order in which stability is maintained through the management of tensions rather than the comprehensive resolution of underlying disputes.

Discussion

The findings presented in Section 3 suggest that ASEAN–China relations in the post–Cold War era cannot be adequately understood through traditional international relations models such as hard balancing or bandwagoning. Instead, they reflect a complex pattern in which cooperation and competition coexist under conditions of pronounced power asymmetry. This perspective yields several important theoretical and practical implications for the study of regional order and actor behavior in an evolving strategic environment.

First, the findings reinforce the argument that ASEAN functions as a regional governance actor through the norms and institutional practices associated with the “ASEAN Way.” Rather than relying on coercive power, ASEAN operates through consensus, non-interference, and preventive diplomacy, thereby creating an institutional space that enables interaction and conflict management among regional actors (Acharya, 2001; Caballero-Anthony, 2022). In its relations with China, this role is evident in ASEAN's leadership in dialogue mechanisms and its promotion of frameworks such as the DOC. This suggests that ASEAN's effectiveness should not be evaluated in terms of its ability to resolve disputes conclusively, but rather in its capacity to maintain stability and prevent escalation.

Second, the study contributes to the understanding of China's behavior as a rising power. The findings indicate that China does not pursue a straightforward strategy of overturning the existing regional order; instead, it adopts a flexible approach that combines institutional engagement with the protection of core strategic interests. This aligns with existing research suggesting that China participates in regional institutions to stabilize its external environment while avoiding commitments that could constrain its ability to adjust behavior in accordance with shifting power dynamics (Johnston, 2003; Goldstein, 2005; Zha, 2023). In this sense, regional institutions are not instruments for constraining great powers, but rather arenas of negotiation where actors adjust their behavior within certain limits.

Third, from the perspective of small and medium-sized states, ASEAN–China relations illustrate a pattern of strategic adaptation commonly conceptualized as “hedging.” Rather than choosing between balancing and alignment, ASEAN countries combine economic cooperation with strategic caution in order to maximize benefits and minimize risks (Goh, 2016; Kuik, 2021). This helps explain why ASEAN simultaneously deepens economic engagement with China while maintaining relations with other major

powers amid intensifying U.S.–China competition (Ha & Hung, 2025). ASEAN’s strategy, therefore, is not passive but reflects a proactive and adaptive approach.

Fourth, the findings highlight the stabilizing role of economic cooperation in ASEAN–China relations. Increasing interdependence through trade and investment has generated shared interests that reduce incentives for direct confrontation (Goldstein, 2005). However, this interdependence is asymmetrical, as China holds significant advantages in economic scale and capacity. This creates a paradox: while economic ties foster cooperation, they also generate concerns about dependence and influence, particularly among ASEAN states (Seah et al., 2024).

Fifth, the analysis underscores the limitations of institutional mechanisms in managing conflict. Although frameworks such as the DOC contribute to maintaining relative stability, they lack the capacity to resolve underlying disputes, especially when core strategic interests are at stake (Buszynski, 2003; Fravel, 2011). This reflects a key characteristic of regional governance under conditions of power asymmetry: institutions can regulate behavior but are unlikely to transform the underlying distribution of power (Mearsheimer, 2001).

Finally, the study suggests that ASEAN–China relations can be conceptualized as a form of “managed asymmetric cooperation,” in which stability is maintained through a balance between cooperation and competition. However, the sustainability of this model depends on several conditions, including ASEAN’s ability to maintain internal consensus, China’s continued institutional engagement, and the broader dynamics of great power competition (Acharya, 2014; Zha, 2023). Should these conditions shift, the space for cooperation may contract, increasing the risk of polarization and regional instability.

Overall, the discussion demonstrates that ASEAN–China relations are not merely a specific case of regional cooperation, but also provide a broader illustration of how actors operate within an asymmetric order, where power, institutions, and strategy interact to shape outcomes.

Conclusion

This article has examined the evolution of ASEAN–China relations in the post–Cold War period as a transition from mutual suspicion to the emergence of an asymmetric cooperation model. By combining historical and institutional analysis, the study demonstrates that the relationship does not follow a linear trajectory of either pure cooperation or confrontation. Instead, it reflects an intermediate condition in which cooperation and competition coexist under increasingly pronounced power asymmetry.

The findings indicate that ASEAN has played a significant role in regulating its relationship with China through regional institutional mechanisms and the norms associated with the “ASEAN Way.” Rather than engaging in direct confrontation, ASEAN has adopted a flexible approach based on consensus and preventive diplomacy to maintain regional stability (Acharya, 2001; Caballero-Anthony, 2022). At the same time, China has participated in these mechanisms selectively, seeking both to stabilize the regional environment and to preserve its strategic autonomy (Johnston, 2003; Goldstein, 2005).

Another key finding concerns the central role of economic cooperation in sustaining ASEAN–China relations. The growth of interdependence through trade and investment has generated shared interests that help reduce the likelihood of direct confrontation. However, this interdependence is asymmetrical, reflecting disparities in economic capacity between China and ASEAN member states, and simultaneously generating concerns about strategic influence within the region (Seah et al., 2024).

Building on these findings, the article argues that ASEAN–China relations can be conceptualized as a form of “managed asymmetric cooperation,” in which institutional mechanisms play a regulatory role but cannot fully eliminate conflict. The sustainability of this model depends on several conditions, including ASEAN’s ability to maintain internal consensus, China’s level of institutional engagement, and the broader dynamics of great power competition (Acharya, 2014; Zha, 2023).

In terms of policy implications, the study suggests that ASEAN should continue to strengthen its centrality and enhance its institutional coordination capacity in order to adapt to an increasingly complex strategic environment. At the same time, maintaining a balance between cooperation and strategic autonomy will remain a critical priority for Southeast Asian states in their relations with China.

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